

Participant ID	Raw data	Codes	Codes #2 iteration	Concept	Sub-Category	Category
G2	Interviewer: Which part confuses users? Participant: Changing health facilities (faskes) or choosing a doctor. Many users don't know they can switch providers every three months.	Confusion about provider-switching rules	No clear guidelines for provider-switching	Ambiguous institutional policy		Institutional and workflow constraints on mHealth uptake
G1	Interviewer: Is the BPJS call center responsive? Participant: They are responsive, but not always fast. It depends on urgency	Variable responsiveness of help center based on urgency	Variable help-center responsiveness	Support responsiveness gaps		
G2	Interviewer: What about referral features? Participant: Yes, but not as often as patient input. Referral quotas are limited.	Limited referral quota	Limited referral quota information	Opaque referral information		
G1	But the queuing system still has problems. It's unclear when referrals become active.	Uncertainty in referral activation timing	Uncertainty in referral activation			
G2	Interviewer: There is also a bed availability feature—do patients use it? Participant: We don't know if the data is real-time. Doctors only use referral features for non-emergency cases.	Poor information quality	Poor information quality and transparency	Administrative workflow uncertainty		
G1	Participant: Yes. Some have low-spec phones and can't install the app due to limited storage.	Technical limitations due to low-spec devices	Low-spec or unsupported devices	Hardware access limitations		Infrastructure and technical constraints undermining reliable use
G2	Participant: Technology helps record keeping and reduces missing data. The challenge is digital literacy—some users resist technology or don't own smartphones. But overall, digital apps are useful.	No access to smartphones	No access to smartphones			
G2	Participant: Benefits: faster process, organized data, reduces lost records. Challenges: digital literacy and unstable internet in some locations.	Unstable internet connection	Unstable internet connection	Network/internet instability		
G1	But there is one drawback: if one admin opens the app, another person cannot open it at the same time. The app cannot be opened by two or three people simultaneously. That's the problem.	Multi-user Restriction	Multi-user Restriction	Shared device constraints		
G1	Unlike WhatsApp—you can duplicate the account on multiple devices. With JKN, you can't, so it slows us down.					
G1	The app logs out frequently and requires re-inputting NIK	Frequent logout	Frequent logout	Session management weaknesses		
G2	Interviewer: If you could improve Mobile JKN, what would you change? Participant: Simplify the interface, larger text, show only frequently used features on the main page. Too many icons clutter the screen.	Screen clutter due to excessive icons	Cluttered interface	Cognitive overload from interface complexity		Interface usability and accessibility constraints
G1	Participant: Yes, because: - Text size is small. - Interface has too many colors and is visually overwhelming.	Overwhelming Interface	Overwhelming interface			
G2	Participant: Text is small, especially on phones. Navigation can be confusing for first-time users.	Confusing navigation for first time users	Confusing navigation	Navigation confusion		
G1	Participant: Yes, because: - Text size is small. - Interface has too many colors and is visually overwhelming.	Small text size	Small text size	Accessibility issues		
G2	Text is small, especially on phones. Navigation can be confusing for first-time users.					
G2	Interviewer: If you could improve Mobile JKN, what would you change? Participant: Simplify the interface, larger text, show only frequently used features on the main page. Too many icons clutter the screen.	Preference for larger text size	Preference for larger text			
G2	Interviewer: If you could improve Mobile JKN, what would you change? Participant: Simplify the interface, larger text, show only frequently used features on the main page. Too many icons clutter the screen.	Preference for simple UI	Preference for simple UI	User preference for simpler design		
G1	Participant: Correct. Better to keep what's essential. --- Interviewer: Would simpler UI with larger fonts and simpler colors help, since many users are elderly?					
G1	Simplify the interface and visual design.					
G1	Only keep essential features.					
G2	Interviewer: Any additional benefits or challenges? Participant: Benefits: faster process, organized data, reduces lost records. Challenges: digital literacy and unstable internet in some locations.	Limited digital literacy	Limited digital literacy	Digital literacy deficiency		User capability and support constraints in mHealth adoption
G2	Interviewer: How does Mobile JKN compare to before it existed? Participant: Technology helps record keeping and reduces missing data. The challenge is digital literacy—some users resist technology or don't own smartphones. But overall, digital apps are useful.	Limited digital literacy as usage barrier				
G1	Interviewer: Why do you think many features are unused? Participant: Because those who can use the features easily are usually under 50 years old.	Age-related digital divide	Age-related digital divide	Age-related technology gap		
G1	Many of my patients are elderly. The app is usually operated by their family members. Their focus is just queuing, referrals, treatment—other features aren't used.					
G2	Interviewer: Is telehealth used often? Participant: Yes, among younger users. Elderly patients prefer direct consultation because they trust face-to-face examination more.					
G2	Interviewer: Are there groups of users who struggle more? Participant: Elderly people and those without tech-savvy caregivers.	Vulnerability of elderly and unsupported users				
G2	Interviewer: Are there groups of users who struggle more? Participant: Elderly people and those without tech-savvy caregivers.		Dependence for caregiver	Dependence on external support		
G1	Some prefer offline consultations—direct education or services. If the family is confused, they go to the clinic and the PIC helps.	Preference for in-person support	Prefer in-person help support	Hybrid model preference		Relational and support model preferences

G2	Interviewer: When patients struggle, who do they contact? Participant: They usually ask admin or assistants—not the call center.						
G2	Interviewer: Is telehealth used often? Participant: Yes, among younger users. Elderly patients prefer direct consultation because they trust face-to-face examination more.	Preference for face-to-face consultation	Preference for face-to-face consultation				
G2	Interviewer: How does Mobile JKN compare to before it existed? Participant: Technology helps record keeping and reduces missing data. The challenge is digital literacy—some users resist technology or don't own smartphones. But overall, digital apps are useful.	Enhanced record-keeping and data accuracy	Enhanced record-keeping	Data quality enhancement	Perceived value and adoption drivers of mHealth use		
G2	Interviewer: Any additional benefits or challenges? Participant: Benefits: faster process, organized data, reduces lost records . Challenges: digital literacy and unstable internet in some locations.						
G2	Interviewer: How does Mobile JKN compare to before it existed? Participant: Technology helps record keeping and reduces missing data . The challenge is digital literacy—some users resist technology or don't own smartphones. But overall, digital apps are useful.	Improved data accuracy	Improved data accuracy				
G1	Interviewer: Do patients give feedback like, "Mobile JKN makes things easier"? Participant: Yes. Many say it's better because they don't need to queue for long.	Reduced waiting time	Reduced waiting time	Workflow efficiency improvement			
G2	Interviewer: Any additional benefits or challenges? Participant: Benefits: faster process , organized data, reduces lost records. Challenges: digital literacy and unstable internet in some locations.	Fast process	Faster processes				
G1	Yes, PeduliLindungi. SatuSehat exists, but it's more for syncing data—tracking hospital visits or vaccine history.	Key functions of mobile health	Key features helpful for patients	Feature-driven usage motivation			
G1	Except for Mobile JKN. With Mobile JKN, BPJS requires us to use it. It must be connected— for referrals, consultations, selecting hospitals or doctors.						
G1	Interviewer: Does Mobile JKN include medical records? Participant: Yes, Mobile JKN has medical records . But the medical records belong to BPJS, not to the doctor personally.						
G1	Interviewer: There are many features. Do patients use all of them? Participant: No, they don't use all the features. Mostly just online queueing, handling referrals, or transferring hospital choices.	Key app features by health workers	Key functions frequently used by GPs				
G1	I've also used another Indonesian private app, but it's not for chatting—only for electronic medical records because it's a requirement for the practice license (SIP).						
G1	But the app I actually interact with the most is Mobile JKN, since I work with BPJS. In our clinic, we have an admin called a PIC admin. They are the ones who fill in the medical records.						
G2	Participant: My assistant handles most of the app usage, but the features we use are: telemedicine (chat consultation), patient input, and the patient rating feature.						
G2	Interviewer: What about referral features? Participant: Yes, but not as often as patient input. Referral quotas are limited.						
G2	Interviewer: Do you use Mobile JKN to fill medical records? Participant: Yes. Complaints, physical exams, diagnosis, and medication must be entered in Mobile JKN.						
G2	Interviewer: Besides Mobile JKN, have you used Halodoc, Alodokter, or SATUSEHAT? Participant: Halodoc and Alodokter are for doctors who register for consultation. SATUSEHAT is used for professional administration: certificates, practice license, continuing education credits.						
G1	Some users have login or registration difficulties. Is registration easy? Participant: It's easy. They just use their NIK. I only need to teach them once.				National ID number as username	National ID number as username	Username recall simplification via national ID
G2	Interviewer: Any issues with login or registration? Participant: Earlier versions required BPJS numbers. Now login using NIK makes it easier.						
G2	Interviewer: So NIK is enough to log in? Participant: Yes. Even without the BPJS card, NIK can retrieve data.						
G2	Participant: Ideally they help, but in practice we only use a few. Too many expectations are placed on doctors with limited reward value. We mainly use telehealth and online queueing.	Excessive workload for healthworkers					
G1	Interviewer: Have you used those apps? Participant: I registered and was accepted, but I didn't continue because it was too much work. I already have a workload from BPJS.						